

A Low-Resource Bengali Language Intelligence Platform for Summarization and Zero-Shot Classification

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Abstract

This paper presents a Low-Resource Bengali Language Intelligence Platform for Summarization and Zero-Shot Classification named as BhashaMind. This is an open source Bengali language processing platform designed to address the challenges of natural language understanding in low-resource settings. Leveraging state-of-the-art multilingual large language models (LLMs), BhashaMind provides robust support for tasks such as abstractive text summarization and zero-shot text classification, with a particular focus on the Bengali language. The system is implemented using a scalable, production-ready full-stack architecture comprising a FastAPI-based Python back-end for inference, a Spring Boot-powered Java API gateway, and a responsive React front-end for user interaction. Through the integration of pre-trained transformer models such as XLM-RoBERTa and BanglaT5, BhashaMind enables efficient language processing capabilities even in the absence of large annotated corpora. The platform is built with modularity, deployment readiness, and accessibility across platforms in mind, making it suitable for academic research, government use, and real-world applications in South Asia and other multilingual regions.

Keywords: Bengali language processing, low-resource languages, zero-shot classification, abstractive summarization, multilingual LLMs, microservices

1 Introduction

Natural Language Processing (NLP) has seen transformative advances as a result of the emergence of large language models (LLMs) trained on extensive multilingual corpora. [1, 2] However, most of these models exhibit sub-optimal performance in low-resource languages such as *Bengali*, despite its status as one of the most spoken languages in the world. The lack of labeled datasets, under representation in model training, and limited tooling pose significant barriers to advancing Bengali-centric NLP research and deployment. [3]

To address these challenges, we present BhashaMind, a full-stack Bengali language intelligence platform designed to bridge this gap through zero-shot and low-resource learning approaches. BhashaMind harnesses the capabilities of state-of-the-art multilingual transformer models such as XLM-RoBERTa [2] and optionally fine-tuned models like BanglaT5 [4] to perform abstractive text summarization and zero-shot classification on Bengali texts. By embedding these models within a scalable and modular microservices architecture, our system supports real-time inference, extensibility, and integration into downstream applications.

1.1 The threefold approach:

- **End-to-End Prototype:** We develop and release a fully functional open source system that incorporates FastAPI (Python), Spring Boot (Java), and React (JavaScript) for seamless data flow and human interaction.
- **Multilingual Model Adaptation:** We investigated the applicability of multilingual LLMs to Bengali without the need for task-specific fine-tuning, demonstrating competitive performance through zero-shot inference.
- **Engineering for deployment:** We optimize the stack for real-world deployment via Docker-based orchestration, GPU acceleration, persistent volume support, and future readiness for asynchronous inference with queuing systems.

In this paper, we detail the design, implementation, and performance of BhashaMind. Our goal is to demonstrate that responsible engineering and careful integration of multilingual models can meaningfully accelerate the NLP capability in underrepresented languages.

2 Related Work

Recent advances in multilingual large language models (LLMs) have significantly improved natural language understanding in low-resource settings. Models such as XLM-RoBERTa have demonstrated strong zero-shot transfer capabilities across over 100 languages, including Bengali. [2]

In the Bengali NLP space, early summarization systems predominantly used extractive methods such as TF-IDF and graph-based ranking. [5] proposed an extractive pipeline combining lexical features and transformer-based scoring. [6] developed one of the first abstractive summarization models for Bengali using bidirectional RNNs with attention, setting a foundation for generative models. A comprehensive overview of multi-document summarization was presented by [7], reflecting increasing interest in robust content aggregation in Bengali.

In Bengali-specific research, notable efforts include the development of BanglaBERT, a monolingual BERT variant trained on a curated corpus of Bengali texts to improve linguistic representation for the language [8]. Similarly, BanglaT5 has extended the encoder-decoder transformer architecture to Bengali by fine-tuning on summarization and translation tasks. [4]

While these models offer strong task-specific performance, they are primarily released as pre-trained checkpoints without integrated deployment frameworks. Broader initiatives like AI4Bharat have focused on dataset curation and multilingual benchmarks for Indian languages, including Bengali. [9].

3 Methodology

BhashaMind integrates modern deep learning techniques with robust engineering to form a complete NLP pipeline for Bengali. The architecture builds on three synergistic pillars: model-level inference, microservice orchestration, and deployment-aware infrastructure.

3.1 Abstractive Summarization with Fine-tuned BanglaT5

We adopt **BanglaT5**, a Bengali-specific T5 model [4], pre-trained in a text-to-text format. For summarization, we fine-tune it on curated Bengali datasets from news, Wikipedia, and editorials. We compute the cross-entropy loss between the predicted and ground-truth tokens for supervised training of the summarizer, as standard in neural generation models. [10]

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}} = - \sum_{t=1}^T \log P(y_t | y_{<t}, x)$$

During inference, beam search decoding [11] (beam width = 4) is applied for improved summarization quality. It is summarized in Algorithm 2.

3.2 Zero-shot Classification via XLM-RoBERTa

For classification, we employ **XLM-RoBERTa Large XNLI** [2], capable of zero-shot prediction without task-specific training. It frames classification as textual entailment. Given a sentence S and candidate label L_i , we construct the hypothesis: “This text is about L_i .” Then, we compute entailment probability:

$$P_{\text{entail}}(S, L_i) = f_{\theta}(S, \text{Hypothesis}_i)$$

The label with the highest entailment score is selected. It is summarized in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Zero-shot Classification using XLM-R

Require: Input text T , Candidate labels $L = \{L_1, L_2, \dots, L_n\}$, Pretrained NLI model f

- 1: **for** each L_i in L **do**
 - 2: Construct hypothesis $H_i \leftarrow$ “This text is about L_i ”
 - 3: Compute entailment score $e_i \leftarrow f(T, H_i)$
 - 4: **end for**
 - 5: **return** $\arg \max_i e_i$ as predicted label
-

Algorithm 2 Abstractive Summarization with BanglaT5

Require: Input text T , Pretrained model M (BanglaT5)

- 1: Preprocess input $T' \leftarrow \text{tokenize}(T)$
 - 2: Encode input $E \leftarrow M.\text{encode}(T')$
 - 3: Generate summary tokens $S \leftarrow M.\text{generate}(E)$
 - 4: Decode S to natural language summary S'
 - 5: **return** Summary S'
-

3.3 Backend and Model Serving Infrastructure

We implement a modular backend design:

- **FastAPI (Python)** for model inference, preprocessing, and GPU dispatch.
- **Spring Boot (Java)** as an API Gateway managing routing and REST endpoints.
- **React (JavaScript)** frontend for real-time interaction and visualization.

Algorithm 3 Prototype Inference Deployment Pipeline

Require: User input T

- 1: Frontend sends T to Spring Boot API Gateway
 - 2: API Gateway forwards request to FastAPI backend
 - 3: Backend routes T to appropriate model service:
 - 4: **if** task = summarization **then**
 - 5: $S \leftarrow \text{BanglaT5}(T)$
 - 6: **else**
 - 7: $L \leftarrow \text{XLM-R}(T)$
 - 8: **end if**
 - 9: API Gateway collects and sends response to UI
 - 10: **return** Output (summary or label)
-

3.4 Dataset Curation and Preprocessing

To address the scarcity of high-quality Bengali NLP resources, we constructed a hybrid dataset by combining manually curated and publicly available sources:

- **News Articles:** Bengali news articles were scraped and annotated from *Anandabazar Patrika* (India) [12] and *Prothom Alo* (Bangladesh) [13], both of which provide rich textual content in formal Bengali. Headlines and summaries were used as parallel pairs for summarization.
- **Wikipedia Articles:** Bengali Wikipedia [14] dumps were tokenized and filtered to generate domain-agnostic samples with clean linguistic structure.

- **AI4Bharat Corpora:** We included Bengali corpora from AI4Bharat¹ which offers a multilingual benchmark suite across Indic languages, especially useful for classification benchmarking.

Table 1 BhashaMind Dataset Sources and Characteristics

Source	Type	Samples	Purpose
Prothom Alo	News	5,000+	Summarization
Anandabazar Patrika	News	4,000+	Summarization
Bengali Wikipedia	Encyclopedia	6,500+	Summarization
AI4Bharat Corpus	Mixed domain	10,000+	Classification

All textual data underwent Unicode normalization, [15] sentence-level tokenization via the Indic NLP library, [16] and aggressive filtering to remove non-Bengali or code-switched content. [17] The resulting dataset spans multiple domains including politics, health, and finance.

3.5 Performance Considerations

The system supports:

- GPU inference via CUDA-enabled containers.
- Batch processing for throughput optimization.
- Health-checks (e.g., `/health` endpoints) for service observability.
- `.env` files for configurable ports, models, and paths.
- Persistent volumes for logs and intermediate storage.

3.6 Workflow Overview

Figure 1 shows the flow of user input through the React frontend, Spring Boot gateway, FastAPI backend, and inference models.

- Summarization requests route to fine-tuned BanglaT5.
- Classification requests are processed by XLM-RoBERTa using textual entailment.

¹The corpus details can be accessed at <https://indicnlp.ai4bharat.org/pages/home/>

3.7 End-to-End Pipeline

Fig. 1 The flowchart of the proposed system incorporating the end-to-end pipeline.

Each user request follows this flow:

1. Input submission via React UI.
2. Routing through Spring Boot gateway to backend.
3. Model inference in FastAPI using selected LLM.
4. Output returned to frontend for display.

This above is summarized in Algorithm 3. **BhashaMind** supports extensibility for future use cases, including async queuing (e.g., RabbitMQ) and multilingual pipelines.

4 System Design

BhashaMind is architected as a full-stack, modular NLP platform tailored for low-resource language processing, with a specific focus on Bengali. The system adopts a microservices-based design that enables flexibility, scalability, and ease of deployment across diverse environments.

4.1 Architectural Overview

The platform comprises three major components:

- **Frontend:** A responsive web interface built using React and TailwindCSS, designed for interactive NLP tasks such as summarization and classification. [18] It supports real-time visualization of outputs and user input submission via a clean, accessible UI.

- **API Gateway:** A central orchestrator implemented in Spring Boot (Java) that routes requests to the appropriate backend services. It handles authentication, rate limiting, and exposes REST endpoints under a unified `/api` namespace.
- **NLP Backend:** A Python-based FastAPI service that encapsulates model inference logic. It loads multilingual transformer models such as XLM-RoBERTa for classification and BanglaT5 for abstractive summarization, optionally leveraging GPU acceleration for performance.

4.2 Microservice Interactions

Requests initiated from the frontend are routed through the API Gateway, which then communicates with the FastAPI backend using HTTP/JSON interfaces. Each microservice is containerized and deployed via Docker Compose, enabling modular scaling and fault isolation.

Data is processed in an end-to-end fashion: user input is preprocessed, passed to the appropriate model, and the prediction result is returned through the gateway to the frontend in a seamless round-trip. [19]

4.3 Deployment and Orchestration Pipeline

The BhashaMind system supports modular deployment using Docker Compose, with container-level health monitoring and future extensibility for asynchronous request handling via message brokers such as Redis or Kafka. The deployment logic and runtime behavior are summarized in Algorithm 4.

4.4 Deployment Optimization

BhashaMind’s deployment strategy emphasizes modularity, portability, and production resilience. The entire pipeline is containerized using Docker, ensuring consistent environment replication across development, staging, and cloud inference clusters. Each component frontend, gateway, and backend is deployed as a discrete service, allowing independent scaling and rapid fault isolation.

To streamline infrastructure provisioning and configuration, the system adopts environment-driven templating via `.env` files and supports parameterization of model paths, inference timeouts, and API ports. Observability is enabled through integrated health-check endpoints (e.g., `/health` for FastAPI), which facilitate uptime monitoring and orchestration by external tools such as Kubernetes or Docker Swarm. [20, 21]

Persistent storage volumes are mounted to retain logs, output predictions, and debugging artifacts across container lifecycles. Furthermore, the architecture anticipates asynchronous expansion, with future support planned for message brokers such as RabbitMQ or Kafka to enable task queuing, load balancing, and eventual micro batch inference in distributed systems. [22]

Algorithm 4 Deployment and Health Management of BhashaMind Microservices

```
1: Services: frontend, api-gateway, nlp-backend, redis/kafka, logger
2: Tooling: Docker Compose, Healthcheck endpoints, Optional message broker
3: procedure STARTPIPELINE
4:   for all service  $s \in$  docker-compose.yml do
5:     DOCKER.START( $s$ )
6:     HEALTHCHECK( $s$ )
7:   end for
8:   Wait for all services to report healthy
9: end procedure
10: procedure HEALTHCHECK( $s$ )
11:    $endpoint \leftarrow$  service URL + /health
12:    $status \leftarrow$  HTTP.GET( $endpoint$ )
13:   if  $status \neq$  200 OK then
14:     RESTART( $s$ )
15:   end if
16: end procedure
17: procedure ASYNCQUEUEHANDLER
18:   while broker is active do
19:      $task \leftarrow$  BROKER.CONSUME ▷ e.g., Kafka or Redis
20:     HANDLEREQUEST( $task.text$ ,  $task.type$ )
21:     LOGMETRICS( $task.id$ , latency, result)
22:   end while
23: end procedure
```

5 Experiments

5.1 Experimental Setup

The BhashaMind system was deployed and tested in two hardware configurations: Local Machine: ASUS Vivobook equipped with Intel Core i7 (13th Gen), 16GB RAM, and NVIDIA RTX 4060 GPU (8GB VRAM). Cloud Deployment (Optional): NVIDIA T4 GPU environment with 4 vCPUs and 32GB RAM via Google Colab Pro and Kaggle kernels for remote evaluation. All services - FastAPI backend, Spring Boot API Gateway, and React frontend - were containerized using Docker, with GPU inference enabled via `nvidia-docker` for model acceleration.

5.2 Task-specific Configuration

Summarization: We used the `banglat5_small` model fine-tuned on news-style Bengali text. Preprocessing included Unicode normalization and sentence segmentation. **Classification:** The zero-shot classification task utilized `xlm-roberta-large-xnli`, leveraging hypothesis templates such as "*This text is about {}*" across Bengali topic labels (translated into English internally).

5.3 Evaluation Metrics

We evaluate BhashaMind across two dimensions: model-level prediction quality and system-level performance metrics. The following statistical measures were employed for objective benchmarking.

5.3.1 Model Accuracy and Quality

Summarization Evaluation.

The quality of generated summaries was measured using the ROUGE metric family - specifically, ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, and ROUGE-L implemented [23] via Hugging-Face’s `evaluate` package. Let S_{gen} be the generated summary and S_{ref} be the reference summary. Then:

$$\text{ROUGE-N} = \frac{\sum_{n\text{-gram} \in S_{\text{gen}} \cap S_{\text{ref}}} \text{Count}(n\text{-gram})}{\sum_{n\text{-gram} \in S_{\text{ref}}} \text{Count}(n\text{-gram})}$$

$$\text{ROUGE-L} = \frac{\text{LCS}(S_{\text{gen}}, S_{\text{ref}})}{|S_{\text{ref}}|}$$

Where LCS denotes the longest common subsequence. To account for statistical variability, we compute:

$$\mu_{\text{ROUGE-1}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N R_1^{(i)}, \quad \sigma_{\text{ROUGE-1}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (R_1^{(i)} - \mu)^2}$$

A ****paired t-test**** between BhashaMind and baseline (mBART-50) systems yielded:

$$t = \frac{\bar{d}}{s_d/\sqrt{n}}, \quad p < 0.05$$

showing statistical significance in summary quality improvement over baseline.

Classification Evaluation.

Let y_i be the true label and \hat{y}_i be the predicted label for $i = 1, \dots, n$. Then:

$$\text{Accuracy}_{\text{Top-1}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbb{1}(y_i = \hat{y}_i)$$

We also compute the ****macro-averaged F1-score****:

$$\text{F1}_{\text{macro}} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{2 \cdot \text{Precision}_k \cdot \text{Recall}_k}{\text{Precision}_k + \text{Recall}_k}$$

where K is the number of classes.

The XLM-RoBERTa model achieved:

- Accuracy = 82.1%
- $\text{F1}_{\text{macro}} = 0.79$
- Cohen’s $\kappa = 0.73$, indicating substantial inter-rater agreement.

5.3.2 System Performance

Latency Analysis.

We define latency L as the time from user input submission to UI rendering of the model output. Let L_i be the latency for the i -th request. Then the average latency and standard deviation:

$$\mu_L = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n L_i, \quad \sigma_L = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (L_i - \mu_L)^2}$$

The cloud-deployed summarization endpoint averaged $\mu_L = 380\text{ms}$ with $\sigma_L = 22\text{ms}$.

Throughput and Load.

Using Locust-based simulation, [24] throughput T was defined as:

$$T = \frac{\text{Total Successful Requests}}{\text{Total Time}}$$

Under a concurrency level of 50 users:

- Summarization: $T = 11.2$ req/sec
- Classification: $T = 16.3$ req/sec
- 95th percentile latency: ≤ 510 ms

Load patterns revealed linear scalability under container orchestration with up to 4 replicas and negligible increase in 95th percentile latency.

Fig. 2 Performance of ROUGE vs. latency

5.3.3 Confidence Intervals and Error Analysis

Bootstrap resampling was applied over the test set to derive 95% confidence intervals. For example, for ROUGE-1:

$$CI_{95\%} = \bar{x} \pm z \cdot \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}, \quad z = 1.96$$

This gives: ROUGE-1 = 0.49 ± 0.017 for T4 deployment.

Misclassified examples were further analyzed for class ambiguity and language drift. Nearly 11% of classification mismatches were due to overlapping class boundaries (e.g., "अर्थनीति" vs. "राजनीति")

6 Results and Evaluations

6.1 Statistical Visualization

To gain deeper insights into the system’s robustness and consistency, we present a multi-faceted statistical analysis of the summarization and classification performance (Fig. 6). The boxplot compares ROUGE-1 scores across four models—*BhashaMind (RTX 4060)*, *BhashaMind (T4 GPU)*, *mBART-50*, and *mT5-Base*. It is evident that *BhashaMind-T4* exhibits both a higher median score and lower interquartile range (IQR), suggesting more reliable summarization performance.

Fig. 3 Performance: ROUGE and Accuracy

Fig. 4 Inference Latency (Inverted for Visualization)

Fig. 5 Variance-Aware Evaluation of BhashaMind and Baselines. Left: ROUGE-1 scores across 10 simulated trials for summarization models, showing 95% confidence bands. Right: Classification accuracy with error bars representing standard deviation across validation subsets.

Fig. 6 Statistical analysis of BhashaMind performance: (Left) ROUGE-1 score distribution across models using boxplot, (Center) Violin plot highlighting density of ROUGE-1 scores, (Right) Histogram of classification accuracy (correct vs. incorrect predictions).

The accompanying violin plot [25] illustrates the score density, indicating that BhashaMind’s outputs are more concentrated around the 0.47–0.5 ROUGE-1 region, while the baseline models exhibit heavier tails and bimodal behavior, reflecting instability across samples.

The third panel presents a histogram of per-sample classification accuracy from a 200-sample test corpus annotated manually. [26] While the top-1 classification accuracy exceeds 81%, the tail distribution of errors suggests that ambiguous or overlapping categories (e.g., शिक्षा vs प्रशासन) remain challenging. Such discrepancies may be further reduced via task-specific fine-tuning and domain adaptation.

As shown in Fig. 5, BhashaMind demonstrates consistent performance with narrow confidence intervals across trials. While mBART-50 and mT5 show higher variance, our pipeline maintains robustness in both summarization and classification tasks under different system conditions.

Table 2 Comparison of BhashaMind with Multilingual Baselines on Summarization and Classification Tasks

Model	Metric	RTX 4060 (Local)	T4 GPU (Cloud)	Summarization	Classification
BhashaMind (Ours)	ROUGE-1	0.47	0.49	✓	✓
	ROUGE-L	0.44	0.46	✓	✓
	Accuracy (Top-1)	81.5%	82.1%	–	✓
	Inference Time (ms)	420	380	–	–
mBART-50	ROUGE-1	0.43	0.45	✓	–
	ROUGE-L	0.41	0.44	✓	–
mT5-Base	ROUGE-1	0.44	0.47	✓	–
	ROUGE-L	0.42	0.45	✓	–
	Accuracy (Top-1)	–	78.6%	–	✓
LaBSE	Accuracy (Top-1)	76.4%	77.3%	–	✓
	Inference Time (ms)	460	410	–	–

Note: Results were benchmarked using a dataset of 200 Bengali news samples across multiple domains. All models except **BhashaMind**'s summarizer (fine-tuned BanglaT5) were used in zero-shot mode. LaBSE [27] is a dual-encoder multilingual model optimized for semantic similarity, not summarization. Inference time was averaged across 10 runs per model per hardware profile.

6.1.1 t-SNE Visualization of Embedding Space

To visualize how the multilingual LLM separates categories semantically, we applied t-SNE [28] to the final-layer sentence embeddings generated by XLM-R. As shown in Figure 7, the resulting clusters align well with class labels, reinforcing the model's capacity to learn discriminative features even in low-resource settings.

Fig. 7 t-SNE projection of XLM-RoBERTa embeddings for Bengali news sentences across 7 real-world categories i.e economy, education, health, technology, sports, culture and politics. The distinct clustering illustrates the model’s ability to capture semantic differences even across low-resource Bengali inputs. Examples are sourced from Bengali news platforms such as *Anandabazar Patrika* [12] and *Prothom Alo* [13].

6.2 Statistical Significance and Confidence Intervals

To ensure that the observed improvements in summarization and classification performance are statistically significant, we conducted pairwise hypothesis testing and computed confidence intervals for ROUGE-1 scores.

6.2.1 Hypothesis Testing

We used the non-parametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test [29] to evaluate the difference in per-sample ROUGE-1 scores between BhashaMind-T4 and the closest baseline (mBART-50) [30], under the null hypothesis:

$$H_0 : \text{Median}(BhashaMind - mBART50) = 0 \quad (1)$$

The test yielded a p-value of $p = 0.018 < 0.05$, allowing us to reject the null hypothesis and confirm that the performance improvement of BhashaMind-T4 is statistically significant.

6.2.2 Confidence Intervals

We further computed the 95% confidence interval (CI) for the mean ROUGE-1 score of each model using the standard t-distribution:

$$CI = \bar{x} \pm t_{\alpha/2, n-1} \cdot \frac{s}{\sqrt{n}} \quad (2)$$

where \bar{x} is the sample mean, s is the sample standard deviation, n is the number of samples, and $t_{\alpha/2, n-1}$ is the t-score from the Student’s t-distribution for confidence level $1-\alpha$ and $n-1$ degrees of freedom. These intervals provide a statistically grounded estimation of the model’s ROUGE-1 score variability across samples, aiding in the comparative reliability assessment of different approaches [31, 32]. The resulting 95% CIs are as follows:

- **BhashaMind-T4**: [0.4816, 0.4935]
- **mBART-50**: [0.4300, 0.4414]
- **mT5-Base**: [0.4140, 0.4303]

These intervals reinforce the reliability of BhashaMind-T4 in producing higher-quality summaries across diverse input articles.

Table 3 ROUGE-1 Mean Scores with 95% Confidence Intervals (n = 100)

Model	Mean ROUGE-1	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
BhashaMind-T4	0.4875	0.4816	0.4935
mBART-50	0.4357	0.4300	0.4414
mT5-Base	0.4221	0.4140	0.4303

6.2.3 Discussion

The statistically significant p-value and narrower confidence interval [33], for BhashaMind-T4 indicate not only a performance gain but also a more consistent output across various input types. These results validate the design of the platform and the use of zero-shot multilingual LLMs [2] for low-resource languages like Bengali.

Table 4 Extended BhashaMind Summarization and Classification Examples (with Main Body)

Sl.	Headline (Input)	Main Body (Source)	Generated Summary	Predicted Category
1	শিক্ষামন্ত্রীর ঘোষণা অনুযায়ী স্কুল পুনরায় খোলার প্রস্তুতি	দীর্ঘদিন বন্ধ থাকার পর অবশেষে রাজ্যের সমস্ত বিদ্যালয় খুলতে চলেছে। শিক্ষামন্ত্রী জানান, স্বাস্থ্যবিধি মেনে ধাপে ধাপে বিদ্যালয় খোলা হবে।	আগামী সপ্তাহ থেকে রাজ্যের সমস্ত স্কুল ধাপে ধাপে খুলবে। স্বাস্থ্যবিধি মানার নির্দেশ দেওয়া হয়েছে।	শিক্ষা (Education)
2	বৃষ্টিবিহীন টেস্ট ম্যাচে ভারতের ঐতিহাসিক জয়	অবিরাম বৃষ্টির মধ্যেও ভারতীয় দল দুর্দান্ত খেলেছে। শেষ দিনে ঋষভ পন্থ ও জসপ্ৰীত বুমরার পারফরম্যান্সে ভারত ৫ উইকেটে জয় পায়।	ভারতীয় দলের দুর্দান্ত পারফরম্যান্সে ৫ উইকেটে জয়। পন্থ ও বুমরার অবদান ছিল গুরুত্বপূর্ণ।	খেলাধুলা (Sports)
3	পেট্রোল-ডিজেলের মূল্যবৃদ্ধিতে সাধারণ মানুষের নাভিস্বাস	নিত্যপ্রয়োজনীয় পণ্যের দামে ব্যাপক প্রভাব পড়েছে পেট্রোল ও ডিজেলের মূল্যবৃদ্ধির কারণে। ভোগান্তিতে পড়েছেন সাধারণ মানুষ।	পরিবহন ব্যয় বৃদ্ধির প্রভাবে নিত্যপ্রয়োজনীয় পণ্যের দাম বেড়েছে। সাধারণ মানুষের মধ্যে ক্ষোভ।	অর্থনীতি (Economy)
4	নতুন কৃষি আইনের বিরুদ্ধে পথে নেমেছে কৃষকরা	নতুন কৃষি আইন বাতিলের দাবিতে হাজার হাজার কৃষক রাজধানীর সীমান্তে জমায়েত হয়েছেন। আন্দোলন দিন দিন তীব্র হচ্ছে।	কৃষি আইন প্রত্যাহারের দাবিতে দিল্লির সীমান্তে বিক্ষোভ। আন্দোলন তীব্র হচ্ছে।	কৃষি (Agriculture)
5	কলকাতা আন্তর্জাতিক চলচ্চিত্র উৎসব শুরু হচ্ছে আজ থেকে	আজ থেকে শুরু হচ্ছে ২৮তম কলকাতা আন্তর্জাতিক চলচ্চিত্র উৎসব। উদ্বোধনী অনুষ্ঠানে প্রদর্শিত হবে সত্যজিৎ রায়ের একটি ক্লাসিক সিনেমা।	চলচ্চিত্রপ্রেমীদের জন্য উৎসবের সূচনা আজ। উদ্বোধনী ছবি সত্যজিৎ রায়ের একটি সিনেমা।	সংস্কৃতি (Culture)
6	দেশে নতুন করে চালু হলো ডিজিটাল স্বাস্থ্য মিশন	সরকার ডিজিটাল স্বাস্থ্য পরিচয়পত্র চালু করেছে, যার মাধ্যমে চিকিৎসার ইতিহাস সংরক্ষিত থাকবে এবং সহজে অ্যাক্সেসযোগ্য হবে।	সরকার নতুন ই-হেলথ কার্ড চালু করেছে স্বাস্থ্য তথ্য সংরক্ষণের জন্য।	প্রযুক্তি (মূলত স্বাস্থ্য হওয়া উচিত ছিল) (Technology)
7	জাতীয় শিক্ষা নীতির বাস্তবায়নে রাজ্যের পরিকল্পনা ঘোষণা	রাজ্য সরকার ঘোষণা করেছে যে নতুন জাতীয় শিক্ষা নীতির আওতায় স্কুল ও কলেজগুলির নতুন কাঠামো এবং পাঠক্রম চালু করা হবে।	শিক্ষাপ্রতিষ্ঠানগুলির পুনর্গঠন ও নতুন পাঠক্রম চালু করার পরিকল্পনা।	প্রশাসন (মূলত শিক্ষা হওয়া উচিত ছিল) (Administration)

Note: *Example 6:* The classification প্রযুক্তি is plausible due to the digital context, but স্বাস্থ্য would be more accurate. *Example 7:* Though correctly summarized, the label প্রশাসন misclassifies the education theme. These highlight the ambiguity and nuances of zero-shot predictions. Overall, BhashaMind shows consistent performance with ROUGE-L 0.44–0.46 and Top-1 accuracy 81–82%.

Fig. 8 Extended BhashaMind summarization and classification examples

7 Conclusion

We demonstrated that BhashaMind performs competitively even without domain-specific fine-tuning, leveraging multilingual generalization for Bengali tasks. Through extensive experiments, we showed measurable gains in summary quality (ROUGE-1

up to 0.49) and classification accuracy (Top-1 accuracy above 82%), while maintaining real-time performance with GPU acceleration and scalable Dockerized deployment.

Our results indicate that combining state-of-the-art LLMs with deployment-aware engineering can bridge the performance gap in low-resource languages. Importantly, BhashaMind serves not only as a research prototype but also as a template for real-world integration of NLP services for underrepresented linguistic communities.

8 Future Work

While BhashaMind demonstrates a robust prototype for Bengali NLP applications, several avenues remain for future exploration and enhancement:

- **Fine-tuning with Richer Bengali Corpora:** Though effective in zero-shot settings, we plan task-specific fine-tuning of BanglaT5 and XLM-R using expanded Bengali datasets, building on the success of BanglaT5’s pretraining on 27.5 GB of Bengali text [4].
- **Multimodal Bengali AI:** Future extensions may include OCR and ASR integration to support speech and image inputs, enabling richer interaction modes in low-literacy contexts [4].
- **Knowledge-grounded Generation:** Incorporating structured knowledge sources (e.g., Wikidata/Bengali DBpedia) may enhance factual accuracy in summaries [4].
- **Cross-lingual Transfer and Multi-Indic Support:** Expanding to handle code-mixed Bengali-English inputs and adapting models across Indic languages, guided by the multilingual benchmarks established in IndicNLPSuite [34].

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